

Development and achievements of the scientific school «Scientific Fundamentals of Plant Materials Chemistry and Technology»

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The Institute of Chemistry has a scientific school called «Scientific Fundamentals of Plant Materials Chemistry and Technology» under the leadership of Academician of the Russian Academy of Sciences A.V. Kutchin. In 2024, the school celebrated its 30th anniversary.

The main areas of activity of the scientific school: science foundations of resource-saving and environmentally friendly application of plant raw materials and their components for chemical products and materials production, obtaining new materials and substances creation on the base of plant polymers, fundamental problems of physiologically active compounds production on the basis of natural substances.

The report will present modern development trends and achievements in the complex processing of plant raw materials to obtain new biologically active substances and materials with valuable practical properties and a wide range of purposes.

A technology for the complex processing of coniferous wood greenery has been developed and implemented to obtain natural highly active preparations for agriculture, veterinary medicine and pharmacology. The new technology is based on the emulsion extraction method. Its advantage over traditional ones based on raw material extraction with organic solvents is an increase in the utilization rate of natural compounds, high resource-saving efficiency and environmental safety.

Methods have been developed for obtaining the main components of preparations for monitoring and combating dangerous pests of coniferous forests (bark beetles, bark beetles and longhorn beetles) based on substances of natural origin - aggregation and sex pheromones of these pests.

Innovative pharmaceutical substances based on natural compounds have been developed for the treatment of socially significant diseases. A full cycle of preclinical studies has been conducted. Technological regulations and a dosage form have been developed.

Methods have been developed for obtaining sorption materials for cleaning and restoring natural objects (water bodies, soil covers) from oil pollution, heavy metal ions and other pollutants of anthropogenic origin based on large-tonnage waste from the production and processing of wood.

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